

ASSESSMENT OF SYNTHESIZED AMIDOAMINE'S BACTERICIDAL PROPERTIES IN SOLUTIONS OF DIFFERENT VISCOSITY

**Mursalov N.I.,
Kangarlı A.A.,
Hasanov E.K.,
Agamalyeva D.B.,
Alizada R.A.,
Ahmedova T.N.,
Gasimov V.J.,
Azizbaylı. E.I.**

Ministry of Science and Education, Institute of Petrochemical Processes

Abstract

The petrochemical sector, which encompasses oil refining and processing, has a history of bactericidal activity. This raises significant concerns due to the substantial quantities of manufactured and processed goods that contain high concentrations of corrosive biocomponents. As a result, the production of water-soluble and oil-soluble bactericidal inhibitors to combat sulfate-reducing bacteria (SRB) is crucial for the oil industry. [1-3]

Keywords: sulfate-reducing bacteria, triethylenetetramine, amidoamine

Methodology:

The study presented focuses on the synthesis of organic matter that includes oleic acid and triethylenetetramine (TETA) and a subsequent examination of its bactericidal properties. An amidoamine compound was synthesized through a reaction between the two substances in a 1:1 molar ratio, conducted at a temperature range of 130-140°C.

The resulting amidoamine was found to exhibit good solubility in both water and isopropyl alcohol. The reaction yielded a product with a purity of 98-99%. The identity of the synthesized amidoamine was confirmed using IR spectroscopy.

Figure 3.

IR Spectrum of Synthesized Amidoamine based on Oleic Acid and Triethylene Tetramine (1:1 Molar Ratio)

The IR spectrum showed the following absorbance bands:

722, 1456, 2814, 2852, 2922 cm⁻¹, representing the deformation and valence vibrations of C–H bonds in CH₂ and CH₃ groups;

3006 cm⁻¹, corresponding to the valence vibrations of the C=C bond;

1649 cm⁻¹, reflecting the valence vibrations of the C=O bond;

1550, 3290 cm⁻¹, signifying the deformation and valence vibrations of the N-H bond in the amine group.

The bactericidal activity of the synthesized reagents was evaluated according to the standards of GOST 18963-73. The tests were performed using "Desulfovibrio desulfuricans" species and strain 1143 of sulfate-reducing bacteria (SRB). The bacterial

growth was facilitated by a Postgate B medium, which served as the nutrient medium. [4].

Figure 1 illustrates the graphic representation of the bactericidal efficacy of the synthesized amidoamine against SRB, through the preparation of 10%, 15%, and 20% (N-1, N-2, N-3) solutions in isopropyl alcohol.

Figure 1. Graphic representation of the bactericidal effect of 10, 15 and 20% solutions of amidoamine in isopropyl alcohol (N-1, N-2, N-3)

As depicted in Figure 1, a substantial number of bacterial cells (10^8) were observed in the control medium, which lacked inhibitors. However, the bactericidal activity of inhibitors in different concentrations was observed as follows: 10% and 15% solutions of amidoamine synthesized from oleic acid and triethylenetetramine (TETA) in isopropyl alcohol, at concentrations of 50 and 100 mg/l, reduced the number of bacterial cells from (10^8 - 10^1). Meanwhile, a 20% solution

of amidoamine in isopropyl alcohol, at concentrations of 100 and 200 mg/l, resulted in a complete elimination of the bacterial cells, reducing their number from 10^8 to 0

The reduction rate of SRB was computed by utilizing the following formula (GOST 39-234-89) post the evaluation of the bactericidal properties of the reagents.

$$X \text{ mg/l H}_2\text{S} = \frac{N(J) \times V(J) - N(\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3) \times V(\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)}{V(\text{H}_2\text{O})} \times 17000$$

The bactericidal effect of the reagent was calculated based on the amount of hydrogen sulfide (H_2S) determined through a calculation using a specified formula.:

$$Z = \frac{C_1 - C_2}{C_1} \cdot 100$$

The efficacy of the reagents was determined by comparing the concentration of H_2S in the medium

without inhibitors to the concentration of H_2S in the medium with the inhibitor.

The results of the bactericidal activity tests conducted using 10%, 15%, and 20% solutions (N-1, N-2, N-3) of synthesized amidoamine in isopropyl alcohol, in a 1:1 mol ratio, against sulfate-reducing bacteria are presented in Table 1.

Table I

The Nomenclature and Constituents of Complexes	Density of matter, C-mg/l	Bacterial count (cell count/ml)	H ₂ S quantity mg/l	Bactericidal effect, Z-%
Example-1-IPA-10%	50	10 ¹	29.9	92
	100	10 ¹	17.5	95.3
	200	10 ¹	1.3	99.6
Example-2-IPA-15%	50	10 ¹	21	94.4
	100	10 ¹	10.7	97.1
	200	-	-	100
Example-2-IPA-20%	50	10 ¹	5.2	98.8
	100	-	-	100
	200	-	-	100
Control-I Amount of H₂S in medium without SRB	24 mg/l			
Control-II Amount of H₂S in medium with SRB	375 mg/l			
Control-III-Number of bacteria in nutrient medium	10 ⁸ cell count/ml			

* The experiments designated as Test I and Test II were conducted to determine the quantity of H₂S in bacterial-free and bacterial-inoculated media respectively. The H₂S content in the control medium without sulfate-reducing bacteria (SRB) was measured to be 24 mg/l in Test I. Conversely, the H₂S content in the bacterial-inoculated medium was measured to be 375 mg/l in Test II. The results of the control experiment, Test III, determined the number of bacterial cells in the nutrient medium, which was found to be 10⁸ cell count/ml.

As presented in Table 1, the initial H₂S concentration in the control medium was 375 mg/L. Upon the addition of the amidoamine reagent at a concentration of 200 mg/L, it was observed that N-1 (10% solution of amidoamine in isopropyl alcohol) reduced the H₂S concentration from 375 mg/L to 1.3 mg/L, resulting in a 99.6% decrease. Meanwhile, N-2 and N-3 (15% and 20% solutions of amidoamine in isopropyl alcohol, respectively) effectively reduced the H₂S concentration to 0 mg/L, demonstrating a complete bactericidal effect and ceasing the metabolic activity of the sulfate-reducing bacteria.

It can be deduced from the results of the study that the bactericidal efficacy of the amidoamine increases with increasing solution concentration.

References

1. Y. Duda, R. Govea-Rueda, M. Galicia, H. I. Beltrn, and L. Zamudio-Rivera, Corrosion inhibitors: design, performance, and computer simulations // J. Phys. Chem. B, 2005, Vol. 109 (47), p. 22674-22684
2. Postgate J.R., Campbell L.L. Classification of Desulfovibrio species the non sporulating sulfate-reducing bacteria. Bacteriol. Revs. 1966, Vol. 30, N 4, pp. 732-738
3. D.B. Agamalieva, M.M. Abbasov, V.M. Abbasov, H.Kh. Aliyev. Synthesis of alkylamine complexes derived from maleic acids and study of bactericidal properties // Practice of anticorrosion protection, 2022, Vol. 27, No. 1, P. 42-48
4. D.B. Agamalieva. study of the bactericidal-inhibitory properties of alkylamine complexes derived from succinic acid / materials of the scientific conference "science, technology and development of innovative technologies" dedicated to the 30th anniversary of the independence of turkmenistan aşgabat • ylym • 2021/12/6, p 488-490